

A Comparative Study on Visual Reaction Time (VRT) for Yellow Color between Yoga Performers and Zumba Performers

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Abstract:

Introduction: Exercise, Yoga and Visual reaction time may be associated in a variety of ways, however the connection is not always obvious. The interval between the presentation of a stimulus and the commencement of a response is referred to as reaction time.

Aims and Objective: The present study was done to know the effect of Yoga performers and Zumba performers on Visual Reaction Time (VRT) for Yellow Color.

Method: In the present study after taking informed consent and ethical clearance, data from 50 Yoga performers and 50 Zumba performers (of age group 20- 40 years) were collected and the visual reaction time for yellow colour was measured while performing Zumba and yoga, respectively.

Result: Statistical results reveal that there is no significant difference in the mean value of VRT (yellow color) between Yoga and Zumba Performers.

Conclusion: Since the difference is not statistically significant, we can clearly conclude that yoga and physical exercises (Zumba) both offer unique benefits for cognition and reaction time in their own ways.

Keywords: Yoga, Zumba, Reaction Time, Visual Reaction time, Yellow Color.

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Introduction

Exercise, Yoga and Visual reaction time may be associated in a variety of ways, however the connection is not always obvious. The interval between the presentation of a stimulus and the commencement of a response is referred to as reaction time. Physical fitness, concentration, and stress levels are all elements that can influence it.

The Visual reaction time measures how quickly a person reacts to Visual stimuli such as a Color.

These assessments can be used to investigate working memory, executive control, attention, and other areas of cognitive function.

Aim and Objective

The present study was done to know the effect of Yoga performers and Zumba performers on Visual Reaction Time (VRT) for Yellow Color.

Materials and Methods

In the present study after taking informed consent and ethical clearance and fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria, data from 50 Yoga performers and 50 Zumba performers (of age group 20- 40 years) were collected and the visual reaction time for yellow colour was measured while performing Zumba and yoga respectively Data analysis was done by applying paired t-test on the software SPSS version 20 using reaction time apparatus - "Standardized 608-Audio-Visual Reaction Timer"

Table 1: Age Wise Distribution of the participants

Group	No. of Participants (N)	%
20-25 yrs	14	10%
26-30 yrs	16	11%
31-35 yrs	12	34%
36-40 yrs	10	46%
Total	52	100%

Observation

Below table depicts the category wise mean value of visual reaction time for yellow colour of Yoga and Zumba performers. The mean value of Yoga performers is ± 1.03 whereas of Zumba performers it is ± 1.34 .

Based on the observation it can be said that the mean value of VRT for yoga performers and for Zumba performers is very close hence there no remarkable difference in the mean values of both the performers.

Table 2: on VRT (Yellow Colour) of Yoga and Zumba Performers

Exercise	No of Participant	Mean & Std Deviation	P value @95% Confidence level
Yoga	50	1.038 \pm 0.345	0.067
Zumba	50	1.340 \pm 0.356	

Graph 1: Category wise Mean Value of VRT

For the purpose of hypothesis testing statistical tool independent sample t-test is applied at 95% confidence interval and p value is observed. Statistical results reveal that there is no significant difference in the mean value of VRT (yellow colour) between Yoga and Zumba Performers. So, the Null Hypothesis is accepted against the Alternate hypothesis. It means that there is no significant difference in the mean value of visual reaction time (Yellow Colour) between yoga and Zumba exercisers ($p = .067 > .050$).

Results

There is no significant difference in the mean value of VRT (Yellow Colour) between yoga and Zumba performers.

Discussion

Research in psychology and neuroscience has shown that colors can influence cognitive processes, including reaction times. Aerobic exercises are relaxing exercises which impact the brain as well as cognitive function. In sports-specific training and

competitive circumstances, reaction time is frequently employed as an indicator of improved sensory motor coordination and general fitness.

Yoga and Zumba performers both are having less response time for yellow colour, though its better in yoga performers. Studies have shown that yellow colour generally thought to be energizing and can increase alertness. It might lead to quicker reaction time in some contexts.

Aerobic exercise and yoga both improves reaction time is by promoting better circulation and oxygen delivery to the brain. Physical activity increases heart rate and blood flow, ensuring that the brain receives an adequate supply of oxygen and nutrients. This heightened circulation can enhance neural function, allowing for quicker processing of information and faster reaction times.

Yoga activates parasympathetic nervous system and in turn aids in relaxation and improves the emotional and psychological well-being.

Although, the exact influence of colors on reaction times can vary based on individual perceptions,

cultural associations, and the specific task being performed. Factors like brightness, hue, and saturation also play a role in how colours impact cognitive processes.

Conclusion

In this study we have found out that both yoga and physical exercise (Zumba) are having their positive impact on cognition and reaction time.

Since the difference is not statistically significant, we can clearly conclude that yoga and physical exercises (Zumba) both offer unique benefits for cognition and reaction time in their own ways.

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References

1. Noorjehan begum, Sendil kumaran D, Venkatesh.G, Kulkarni SB (2012) Study of the Utility of Short Course of Yoga to Improve Reaction Time, *Journal of clinical and diagnostic research*,6(7),241-1243.
2. Spierer DK, Petersen RA, Duffy K. The response time to the stimuli in division I soccer players. *J Strength Cond Res.* 2011; 25(4):1134-41.
3. Naik, L. (2021). Effect of yogic relaxation technique on auditory and visual reaction times. *International Journal of Research in Medical Sciences*, 9(5), 1473–1478.